

Raising, Educating, and Portraying Heirs to the Danish Throne at the court of Margaret of Austria

Abstract: Margaret of Austria (1480-1530) was renowned for her excellent political skills, dedicated administration of her dynasty's concerns, and as a patron of the arts. She created an outstanding Renaissance court in Mechelen, where she also took care of relatives who had been ousted from their position as rulers, as was the case for Isabella of Austria and Christian II of Denmark, who were exiled from their kingdom in 1523. The children of this royal couple, members of the Habsburg family, went on to be raised and educated in Mechelen.

To shed light upon the education of the princes, first the attention will be devoted to the schooling of the members of the Habsburg dynasty, the children of Philip the Fair and Juana I of Castile, who spent their early years at Mechelen. Later on, the education and the privacy of Dorothea, John and Christina, the children of Christian II and Isabella of Austria at the Court of Savoy will be analyzed. The paper studies the privileged educational program created for these children to check how scientific knowledge formed part of the syllabus set for the heirs to the Danish throne and how these children also contributed to creating an idealized image of Habsburg heirs.

To answer those questions, the correspondence preserved in the Danish National Archives (Rigsarkivet) and exchanged between Habsburgs between 1523 and 1525 serves as a source. Furthermore, the insight provided by these documents is complemented by an iconographic analysis of the portraits attributed to Jan Gossaert, as this artist met the princes in person, while his representations were inspired by the tradition of child portraiture circa 1500. Although there is a lack of documentation concerning the education of children within the close family milieu during the early decades of the sixteenth century, thanks to the sources examined below some insights may be provided into Renaissance pedagogy, the role given to science and the emerging early modern understanding of the world in private and courtly entourage.

Keywords: Margaret of Austria, Christian II of Denmark, Children education, portraits, Sixteenth century

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Introduction

Following the exile of Christian II of Denmark (1481-1559), his wife Isabella of Austria (1501-1526) left their children in the care of her aunt Margaret of Austria (1480-1530), while the couple traveled to the courts of Europe in search of military support and aid to restore their rights to the Danish throne.¹ Isabella was following the example of her own father, Philip the Fair (1482-1506), who had also left her in the care of his sister Margaret. That was because, following the death of Isabella of Castile (1451-1504), Philip the Fair, heir to the territories of the Emperor Maximilian I (1459-1519), moved with his wife Juana of Castile (1479-1555) to the Iberian Peninsula in order to take up the throne.² During their absence, their children - Eleanor of Austria (1498-1558), Prince Charles (future Emperor Charles V) (1500-1558), Isabella of Austria (1501-1526), and Mary of Hungary (1505-1558) were raised in Mechelen by Margaret of Austria. The same fate awaited the Scandinavian princes John (1518-1532), Dorothea (1520-1580), and Christina (1521-1590), who were to remain in Mechelen starting in 1523. Like their mother, the Scandinavian princes went on to live with Margaret of Austria in one of the most illustrious courts of the day, which was frequented by diplomats, philosophers, and artists sponsored by their great-aunt. It was also there that they had their portraits painted by Jan Gossaert, court painter to the governor of the Low Countries.³

This article seeks to shed light on the relationship between privacy and education for Dorothea, John, and Christina, the princes of Denmark - children of Christian II and Isabella of Austria, during their time at the Court of Savoy, where their upbringing was provided by their great-aunt Margaret of Austria. The analysis of sources on tutors,

¹ L. Bissgaard, *Christian 2. En biografi*, København, 2019, pp. 346-359; M. Lobo Cabrera, *Isabel de Austria. Una reina sin ventura*, Madrid, 2019, pp. 81-94. This text was published as a result of the project funded through 2022/47/D/HS2/01798 - NCN, Poland (Narodowe Centrum Nauki).

² On the archduke's journey to the Iberian Peninsula and their reception there, see: M^a C. Porras Gil, *De Bruselas a Toledo. El viaje de los archiduques Felipe y Juana*, Madrid, 2015; R. Fagel, 'Le découverte de l'Espagne. Philippe le Beau et l'héritage ibérique', in: B. Bousmanne and H. Wijsman, *Philippe le Beau (1478-1506). Le trésors du dernier duc de Bourgogne*, Bruxelles, 2006, pp. 51- 60.

³ L. Campbell, *The Sixteenth Century Netherlandish Paintings, with French Paintings Before 1600*, vol. 1, London, 2014, pp. 344-351; M. Friedländer, *Early Netherlandish Painting*, t. VIII, London, 1972.

readings, the everyday life of children in the palace, and their portraits provide knowledge to understand what their privacy was and how the dynastical custody guaranteed it.

Margaret of Austria had a strong reputation for erudition, patronage of the arts, and interest in education. Since 1504, she had taken up residence in the palace, the Court of Cambrai in Mechelen, and later moved her court across the street to the Court of Savoy.⁴ She and those in her milieu acted as patrons of the arts and commissioned works from artists such as Michel Sittow (c. 1468-1525), Jacopo de Barbari (c. 1445-1516), Bernard van Orley (1487-1541), and Jan Gossaert (1478-1532), among others,⁵ and this patronage also extended to the most illustrious philosophers of the sixteenth century, such as Erasmus of Rotterdam (c. 1467-1536) and Juan Luis Vives (1492-1540).⁶ Aside from playing an active role in the religious disputes of the time, these authors also wrote treatises on education, works whose conventions had become established by the literary genre known as the “mirror of princes”.⁷ Thus, it was in Mechelen, amidst the flourishing Northern Renaissance, where the previous generation of young princes of the Habsburg family, that the children of Philip the Fair and Juana I of Castile, were brought up, and they would only leave the city to fulfil their matrimonial obligations or to take up the reins of power; Leonor of Austria in 1518, Charles in 1517, Isabella in 1515, and Mary in 1514. One generation later, the same education would be given to the exiled Danish princes.

Since there is a limited number of sources specifically about the case of the Danish princes, in this article, the education of the previous generation can provide clues on the role of childhood privacy related to the education provided by the family. An analysis of educational programs of that period also offers an opportunity to consider how the new branches of scientific inquiry, practiced in “private,” were included within the syllabus set for the heirs to the Danish throne and how they also contributed to the creation of an idealized public image – state portrait – of the princes and princesses.⁸

⁴ For further information on the two palaces in Mechelen, see: K. de Jonge, ‘The Principal Residences Mechelen: the Court of Cambrai and the Court of Savoy’, in: D. Eichberger, ed, *Women of Distinction: Margaret of York/Margaret of Austria*, Leuven, 2005, pp. 56-66.

⁵ F. Baudson, *Van Orley et les Artistes de la Cour de Marguerite d’Autriche*, Brou, 1981; D. Eichberger, *Leben mit Kunst - Wirken durch Kunst. Sammelwesen und Hofkunst unter Margarete von Österreich, Regentin der Niederlande*, Turnhout, 2002, pp. 363-365.

⁶ More on Margaret’s court and patronage, see: H. de Ridder-Symoens, ‘Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court’, in: S. Mareel, *Renaissance Children: Art and Education at the Habsburg Court (1480-1530)*, Brussels, 2021, pp. 28-29.

⁷ E. Desiderius, *The Education of a Christian Prince*, Cambridge, 1997, pp. 3-4; H. de Ridder-Symoens, ‘Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court’, (as in n. 6), pp. 28-29.

⁸ More examples of studies on practices of domestic education, see: S. Evangelisti, ‘Learning from Home: Discourses on Education and Domestic Visual Culture in Early Modern Italy’, *History*, 98, 5, 2013, pp. 666-667.

The life and routine of the Danish princes draws on an analysis of the letters exchanged between Isabella of Austria, the mother of John, Dorothea, and Christina, and their aunt Margaret of Austria. Currently, the correspondence forms set in the Danish National Archives (Rigsarkivet) and was exchanged between 1523 and 1525.⁹

Furthermore, the insight provided by these sources is complemented by an iconographic analysis of the portraits attributed to Jan Gossaert, as this artist met the princes in person and created representations of them that were inspired by the tradition of child portraiture circa 1500.¹⁰ Although there is a lack of documentation concerning the education of children, or their private interactions within the close family milieu during the early decades of the sixteenth century, thanks to the sources examined below, insights are provided into Renaissance pedagogy and notions of privacy.

Controlled Publicity: Child Portraiture in the Habsburg Family

It should be noted that the genre of the child portrait began to be disseminated during the final decades of the fifteenth century and the start of the sixteenth, above all amidst royal and aristocratic families, albeit with some exceptions.¹¹ One of the first examples produced in the Netherlands was the double portrait of the sons of Maximilian I, Philip the Fair, and Margaret of Austria, painted possibly by the court painter Pieter van Coninxloo (c. 1460-1513) circa 1493-1495 (fig. 1).¹² Given the historical context and the matrimonial negotiations being undertaken for both princes it may be surmised that this dual portrait was made to present them as potential suitors for the marriages then under consideration. The repetition of this composition and the presence of these works in the sitters' inventories also indicates an emotional tie between them and the painting that symbolically commemorates their intimate family relationship and memory, as well as their state portrait image.¹³

Following the same practice, portraits of the children of Philip the Fair and Juana of Castile were painted as a diptych, later reproduced in various compositions. The Habsburg princes are represented in a stylized manner, verging on a heraldic mode of depiction, against a uniform background; few attributes are alluding to the sitters, such as is also the case in the panels in the Kunsthistorisches Museum in Vienna, painted circa

⁹ Rigsarkivet, København, München-Samlingen, B32, pk. 31, laeg nr. 10.

¹⁰ T-H. Borchert, 'Portraits of Habsburg Children', in: S. Mareel, ed, *Renaissance Children: Art and Education at the Habsburg Court (1480-1530)*, Brussels, pp. 55-56.

¹¹ T-H. Borchert, 'Portraits of Habsburg Children' (as in n. 10), pp. 46.

¹² D. Eichberger, *Leben mit Kunst* (as in n. 5), p. 32-33;

¹³ T-H. Borchert, 'Portraits of Habsburg Children', pp. 46-47.

1502 (fig. 2)¹⁴, or those that once formed part of the Museo de Santa Cruz in Toledo and are thought to be still conserved in the Iberian Peninsula (fig. 3).¹⁵ While Gossaert's portraits of John, Dorothea, and Christina adhere to the same Habsburg mode of child state portrait, they stand out for their distinctive more detailed treatment than of the sitters, which foregrounds the children's erudite education, and this is not only the result of a shift in the artist's approach to the genre, but it is perhaps also due to a change of focus in the domestic education of children, their idealization as the future of the dynasty. The young sitters should understand the importance of their portrait created in the domestic sphere for their image projection as a members of the dynasty.¹⁶

Fig. 1. Attributed to Pieter van Coninxloo, *Diptych with the portraits of Philip the Fair (1478-1506) and his sister Margaret of Austria, 1493-1595*, London, National Gallery, inv. NG2613.1 and 2.

¹⁴ C. Périer d'Ieteren, 'Le triptique de Charles Quint et des ses deux soeures enfans. Un oeuvre du Maître de la Gilde de Saint-Georges', *Bulletin Koninklijk Instituut van het Kunstpatrimonium*, 14 (1973-1974), pp. 105-117.

¹⁵ M.Á. Zalama, 'Felipe el Hermoso y las artes', in M.Á. Zalama and P. Vandernbroeck, *Felipe el Hermoso. La belleza y la locura*, Madrid, 2006, pp. 17-50.

¹⁶ S. Evangelisti, 'Learning from Home: Discourses on Education and Domestic Visual Culture in Early Modern Italy' (as in n. 8), p. 676.

Fig. 2. Master of the Mechelen Guild of Saint George, *Portraits of Eleanor, Charles V and Isabella of Austria as Children*, 1502, Vienna, Kunsthistorisches Museum, Gemäldegalerie, 4452.

Fig. 3. Anonymous, *Sons of Philip the Fair and Juana of Castile*, c. 1500, Unknown location, previously in the collection of the Museo de Santa Cruz, Toledo.

Habsburg Childhood in Mechelen

From 1477 onwards, Margaret of York (1446-1503), the widow of Charles the Bold (1433-1477), resided in Mechelen. She acquired a residence in the city from John of Burgundy (1404-1479), bishop of Cambrai, and remained there until 1486. The Court of Cambrai was later acquired by the city and presented to Philip the Fair as his urban residence. Probably from 1501 onwards, his children, Eleanor, Charles, and Isabella,

resided there.¹⁷ The princes were accompanied by guards, musicians, and veterinarians, their court members. It should be noted that in 1509 the household of the young Habsburgs were divided into two, one for Charles – overseen successively by Henry de Witthem, Charles de Croÿ (1455-1527) and Guillaume II de Croÿ (1458-1521) – and the second for his sisters, which was first managed by Anne of Burgundy (1435-1508), the illegitimate daughter of Philip the Good, and then from 1509 by Anne de Beaumont (c. 1470-after 1523).¹⁸

The Habsburg princes' residence there and their daily life is reflected in a number of documents issued by the city's municipal government, which paid for their upkeep in expectation of a future benefice. Likewise, the documentation for the city's expenditure records the building work undertaken on the Habsburg residence, which included the renovation of the gardens, the purchase of desks, protective window bars for the classrooms where the princes studied, and a new court for playing *jeu de paume*. Then, when one of Prince Charles's ostriche escaped in 1502, the city paid for its recapture. The heirs to the empire also received gifts from the council, such as jewels, sweetmeats, horses, and books. The city organised a number of festivities, which the courts of Cambrai and Savoy took part in, such as processions, banquets and hunting.¹⁹ Those pieces of information explained how the rising of young Habsburgs was not only a dynasty issue but also a public matter for the city and the state. Aside from the young Habsburgs, the court was host to other European princes, such as Massimiliano (1493-1530) and Francesco Sforza (1495-1535), and also Anne Boleyn (c. 1501-1536). The children, were often the subject of letters exchanged between Margaret of Austria and her father, Emperor Maximilian I, and they were described as “les nostres communs enfants”, “noz très chières et très amées filles”, and “enfants d'honneur”.²⁰

¹⁷ A. M., Schegelmilch, *Die Jugendjahre Karls V.: Lebenswelt Und Erziehung Des Burgundischen Prinzen*, Köln, 2011; S. Mareel, 'The Habsburg Children's Household at the Court of Cambrai in Mechelen (1480-1530)', in: S. Mareel, *Renaissance Children: Art and Education at the Habsburg Court (1480-1530)*, Brussels, pp. 14-15.

¹⁸ S. Mareel, 'The Habsburg Children's Household at the Court of Cambrai in Mechelen (1480-1530)' (as in n. 17), p. 15. More on Anne of Burgundy, and Anne de see: R. Domínguez Casas, 'Ana de Borgoña, dama de Ravenstein, "Muger muy granjera y rica", y las exequias de su marido en Bruselas', in M. Á. Zalama; M. C. Porras Gil, eds., *Entre la política y las artes. Señoras del poder*, Madrid, 2022, pp. 45-72, and V. Soen, 'The House of Cröy and Mary of Burgundy' in M. Depreter; J. Dumont; E. L'Estrange; S. Mareel, eds., *Mary of Burgundy. 'Persona, Reign and Legacy of a Late Medieval Duchess*, Turnhout, 2021, pp. 237-250.

¹⁹ S. Mareel, 'The Habsburg Children's Household at the Court of Cambrai in Mechelen (1480-1530)', pp. 19-21.

²⁰ A. Le Glay, *Correspondance de l'empereur Maximilien Ier et de Marguerite d'Autriche, sa fille, gouvernante des Pays-Bas, de 1507 à 1519*, Paris, 1839; L. D. Gelfand, 'What's Love Got to Do with It? Unlacing the Love Knots in Margaret of Austria's Royal Monastery at Brou', in W. S. Melion; J. Woodall; M. Zell, eds, *Ut pictura amor: The Reflexive Imagery of Love in Artistic Theory and Practice, 1500-1700*, Leiden, 2017, pp. 420-424.

In the wake of the death of Philip the Fair, on 18 July 1507 Prince Charles, adorned with the chain of the Order of the Golden Fleece, took part in a procession through Mechelen accompanied by his guards. The following day, the herald announced to the people: “The king is dead” and “Long Live Don Charles”, and the young prince’s sword was used to invest him as the new sovereign.²¹ A year later, on 20 July, Charles, accompanied by Margaret of Austria, attended the General States of Brabant for the first time for the purpose of requesting support for his war against the kingdom of France.²² Aged seven, the prince continued with his education, which consisted of writing, reading, mathematics, and singing. Throughout the Habsburg princes’ childhood at the court, Adriaan Wiele (15th c. - 1530) was employed as *maistre d’escole des enfants d’honneur*, and Charles de Poupet (c. 1460-1530), as their teacher of physical education and riding. Up until 1514, Luis Cabeza de Vaca (1465-1550) served as Charles’s teacher, and he was assisted by Adriaan Boeyens de Utrecht (the future pope Adrian VI) (1459-1523) in 1511.²³ Aside from providing him with a classical education, they attended to the Habsburg prince’s moral and spiritual development. Although Erasmus of Rotterdam and Juan Luis Vives, who had both written treatises on humanist education, resided at the court of Margaret of Austria, neither of them served as Charles’s official teachers, yet they undoubtedly frequented Mechelen.²⁴

As time went by, the young Charles, along with his parents, began to spend more time in Brussels and in Tervuren than in Mechelen, and he distanced himself from his protectress in favour of Guillaume II de Croÿ, Lord of Chièvres, a politician who advocated a solid pact between the Habsburgs and the Valois of France as a forward-looking policy. On coming of age in 1515, Charles chose the palace of Coudenberg in Brussels as his principal residence, thus opting for a new centre of power in the Netherlands, which reaffirmed the success of Guillaume II de Croÿ, Lord of Chièvres.²⁵ It is highly probable that as a result of his close relationship with Guillaume, Charles neglected to improve his

²¹ A. Schoysman, *Jean Lemaire de Belges. Chronique de 1507. Édition critique par Anne Schoysman. Notes historiques et index des noms propres par Jean-Marie Cauchies*, Brussels, 2001, p. 129.

²² A. M., Schegelmilch, *Die Jugendjahre Karls V*, (as in n. 17), p. 88.

²³ A. Pinchart, *Archives des arts, sciences et lettres. Documents inédits publiés et annotés par Alexandre Pinchart, Chef de section aux Archives générales du royaume de Belgique*, Gand, 1860, p. 3.

²⁴ More on the Early Modern Education, see: Ph. Ariès, *L'enfant et la vie familiale sous l'ancien regime*, Paris, 1960; W. Boucher, ‘Pilgrimage to Parnassus: local intellectual traditions, humanists education and the cultural geography of sixteenth-century England’ in *Pedagogy and Power: Rhetorics of Classical Learning*, edited by N. Livingstone and Y. L. Too, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998, pp. 110-47; A. Ross, ‘Schools and education’ in *Early Modern Childhood: An Introduction*, edited by A. French, London: Routledge, 2019, pp. 94-118. For the later reception of Erasmus’ treaty, and an example of its impact in the history of education, see: N. da Silva Perez, ‘Lady Jane Lumley’s Private Education and its Political Resonances’ in *Women’s Private Practices of Knowledge Production in Early Modern Europe*, edited by N. Klein Käfer and N. da Silva Perez, Palgrave-MacMillan, 2023, pp. 18-20.

²⁵ G. Parker, *Carlos V: Una nueva vida del emperador*, Madrid, 2019, p. 13; S. Haliczzer, *The Comuneros of Castile: The Forging of a Revolution, 1475-1521*, Madison, 1981, p. 45.

language skills and instead focused on hunting, tourneys, and physical pursuits. The prince's education ended with his move to Brussels.²⁶

The education of the future emperor's sister was as carefully planned. The libraries owned by the duchesses of Burgundy, Isabella of Portugal (1397-1471), Margaret of York, and later Margaret of Austria, to a large extent, included the books needed to educate their descendants.²⁷ The latter received her education in the French court while in the custodianship of Anne of France (1461-1522), the regent of the kingdom, and author of the instructions *Enseignements d'Anne de France à sa fille Suzanne de Bourbon*.²⁸ In Amboise, Margaret was brought up in the sphere of women considered necessary to equip her with administrative, political, and diplomatic skills. During her time there, she also had her portrait painted by the court painter Jean Hay (c. 1475-c. 1505).²⁹

At Mechelen, Margaret employed the same didactic approach for her nieces, using her private resources for the state's good and dynasty purpose. Confirmation of this is provided by the commission assigned to Jean Loupes of Bruges in 1503; he had to produce a book entitled ABC, which was probably for Eleonor of Austria, who was aged four at the time.³⁰ The princesses' elementary education would not have been very different from that provided for Prince Charles and would have included writing, reading, and music, as well as the rudiments of history and Latin. Later on, their teachers would introduce the study of Greek and Latin, rhetoric, letter writing, poetry, theology, law, and mathematics. Those skills were necessary to perform the role of the ruler. Hendrik Bredemers (1472-1522), a member of Margaret of Austria's chapel, served as the prince and princesses' music teacher. The children learnt to play various instruments, and Eleonor, the eldest, excelled at music. The girl's education did not overlook physical

²⁶ H. de Ridder-Symoens, 'Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court', p. 38.

²⁷ H. Wijsman, 'Femmes, livres et éducation dans la dynastie bourgondo-habsbourgeoise. Trois Marguerites à la loupe' in: J-M. Cauchies, dir, *Publication du Centre Europeen d'estudes Bourguignonnes (XIVe-XVIIe s.), Marguerite d'York et son temps*, Neuchâtel, 2004, pp. 181-198; H. de Ridder-Symoens, 'Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court', pp. 32-34; D. Eichberger, 'Una libreria per donne assai ornata et riccha' – Frauenbibliotheken des 16. Jahrhunderts zwischen Ideal und Wirklichkeit', in: G. Signori, dir., *Die lesende Frau*, Wolfenbüttel, 2009, s. 241-264.

²⁸ T. Clavier, 'Les enseignements d'Anne de France et l'héritage de Christine de Pizan', in: I. Brouard-Arends, ed., *Lectrices d'Ancien Régime. Nouvelle édition*, Rennes, 2003, pp. 23-31.

²⁹ E. L'Estrange, 'Anne de France et le mécénat d'Anne de Bretagne', in: K. Wilson-Chevalier, ed, *Patronnes et mécènes en France à la Renaissance*, Saint-Etienne, 2007, pp. 169-194.

³⁰ *Un livre que l'on appelle ABC, escrit en lettres de formes, garni de bonnes histoires et plusieurs lettres d'or*, A. M., Schegelmilch, *Die Jugendjahre Karls V*, p. 165; H. de Ridder-Symoens, 'Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court', p. 34.

education, which included dancing, horse riding, swimming, and falconry.³¹ The fact that the young Habsburg princesses were educated in a similar manner to their brother demonstrates that they were being prepared for a political role from a young age, as well as to act as a model for their future subjects, and a future sovereign raised in debt to the state. This strategy allows to maintained children as a part of the dynasty, and layered goals that come from the education. The appropriate selection of tutors, providing safety, tools to study and leisure in private, would benefit the future of public and political interests of family members.

Welcoming exiled relatives from Denmark

Following the failure of Christian II of Denmark's domestic policy to meet the promises made at his coronation, which favoured the peasants instead of maintaining the power held by the Scandinavian nobility, a number of noble families rebelled against the monarch. In 1523, the protests came to a head with the nobility's refusal to obey Christian II and the proclamation of his paternal uncle, Frederick I (1471-1533), duke of Schleswig, as king. Following the self-proclamation of Frederick as king of Denmark and Norway and the election of Gustav Vasa (1496-1560) as king of Sweden. Isabella of Austria who was considered to be a legitimate queen by her husband's subjects,³² rejected the proposal that she rule as regent until their son, John, came of age.³³ On 13 April 1523, the king with his family, treasurers, and closest entourage set sail for the Netherlands, where he hoped to receive military and financial support from Isabella's relatives.

The exiled king's stay in Mechelen was intended to obtain a part of Isabella's dowry that remained to be paid by Charles V. Having not received any clear reply from Charles on this matter, the monarchs left their children with Margaret of Austria, and in that same year they travelled to the English court. Unfortunately for them, Isabella's family ties to Henry VIII's wife, Catherine of Aragon (1485-1536), proved insufficient to obtain a loan to pay for a mercenary army.³⁴ Following their return to the continent, the royal couple made their way to Cologne, where they met with Joachim I Nestor (1484-1535), the prince-elect of the Margraviate of Brandenburg, Christian II's son-in-law. The exiled

³¹ H. de Ridder-Symoens, 'Balancing Knightly Ideals and Humanists Appropriateness: Upbringing and Education at the Burgundian-Habsburg Court', p. 36.

³² B. Bennassar, *Reinas y princesas del Renacimiento a la Ilustración. El lecho, el poder y la muerte*, Barcelona, 2007, p. 102.

³³ M. Grönvold, 'Isabel de España, hermana de Carlos V reina de Dinamarca, Noruega y Suecia', *Boletín de la Real Academia de la Historia*, 38, 153 (1958), p. 151.

³⁴ M. Lobo Cabrera, *Isabel de Austria. Una reina sin ventura* (as in .6), p. 83. On the education at the English court related to the commissions of Catherine of Aragon, see: E. L. Cahill Marrón, 'Veritas Temporis Filia: Catalina de Aragón y la transformación de la educación regia femenina' *Atalaya. Revue d'études médiévales romanes*, 20, 2022; M. Smolik, 'Royal education in the Tudor Age', *Lublin Studies in Modern Languages and Literature*, 31, 2007, pp. 193-210.

monarchs also negotiated financial aid from the sovereigns of Brunswick and Saxony as part of their effort to recover their rights over the kingdoms of Denmark and Norway.³⁵

During their voyage across the Holy Roman Empire's territories, on 27 September 1523 an inventory of properties of Isabella of Austria's was drawn up.³⁶ This document corroborates that Isabella's treasury contained jewels and pendants with mythological and biblical subjects akin to those possessed by other queens at that time, showing her taste for the goods. A month later, in Berlin, the queen gave orders for another inventory to be drawn up to sell her possessions and cover her husband's debts. As a result, some of her belongings were sold to Bertil Forcke, Hans von Skonbergh and the merchant Hans,³⁷ and, in January of the following year, to Hans Mickelssen.³⁸

On 22 March 1524 the exiled kings pleaded their cause in Nuremberg before the Imperial Diet, presided over by Ferdinand I Habsburg (1503-1564), Isabella's brother. It was the first meeting between them, as Ferdinand had been born and brought up in the Iberian Peninsula. Once more, this attempt to obtain funds to recover the Scandinavian kingdoms proved unsuccessful. In June of that same year, Isabella returned to Flanders, and she was followed by Christian II a few months later. The governor of the Netherlands granted the couple a residence in Lierre, where they stayed with their children. At the end of 1525, Isabella moved to Zwijnaarde, close to Ghent, where she died on 19 January, following a long illness.³⁹ In early 1526, an inventory of her remaining jewels was drawn up by Johan Dionys in Antwerp and Mechelen. The latter document reveals the possessions conserved in the queen's chamber, which included valuable rings and precious stones.⁴⁰

During the period that Isabella left her heirs in Mechelen and up until her death, she maintained a correspondence with her relatives, with all her brothers and sisters, as well as her aunt Margaret of Austria. The letters sent between Isabella and her aunt consist of twenty-one folios dated between 1523 and 1525, although six are undated. The main matter of those letters is family relations, the progress of looking at the support of the Danish Royal couple, and a few notions on the education and safety of their children. With regard to the princes' upbringing in Mechelen, Margaret of Austria assured their

³⁵ J. Nybo Rasmussen, *Fray Jacobo Daciano*, Michoacán, 1992, p. 111.

³⁶ J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca', in: F. Checa Cremades, *Los inventarios de Carlos V y la familia imperial* vol. 3, 2010, Madrid, pp. 2601-2603.

³⁷ Rigsarkivet, Oslo, München-Samlingen, no. 680-681; J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca' (as in n.28), p. 2625-2627; Rigsarkivet, Oslo, München-Samlingen, no. 530; J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca', p. 2629; Rigsarkivet, Oslo, München-Samlingen, no. 697; J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca', p. 2631-2632.

³⁸ Rigsarkivet, Oslo, München-Samlingen, no. 1003; J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca', p. 2633.

³⁹ Ch. Bo Bramsen, *Isabel 1501-1526. La pincesa hispano-austriaca que llegó a ser reina de Dinamarca*, MAdrdi, 2004, p. 53. Rigsarkivet, København, München-Samlingen, B32, pk. 31, laeg nr. 10.

⁴⁰ Rigsarkivet, København, München-Samlingen, B32, f. 53; J. Hein, 'Isabel de Austria, Reina de Dinamarca', pp. 2635.

mother of their health on various occasions and mentioned her care for them, but she did not give any precise details (15 January 1524). Although the correspondence above all demonstrates the governor of Flanders's concern for her nephew and nieces' health (7 September 1524), it also lists the commissions made for the princes' clothing, which were paid for by their guardian (27 May 1525). In one of the last letters exchanged between the two women, Margaret, aware of Isabella's fragile health, assures her of the well-being of her descendants (25 December 1525).⁴¹ On the one hand, these sources provide little information on the behavior of Isabella's children or details of their daily life, but they document a private dimension within Imperial family circles, as well as the concern shown by relatives for the heirs to the different branches of the family. On the other hand, information about children's good health and few mentions of their well-being show the involvement of privacy-related terms and their ties to the safety of the dynasty's future.

Although the Habsburgs decided not to fund the support requested by Christian II and Isabella to enable them to return to their kingdom, both exiled monarchs used representations of themselves as a potent visual strategy within their campaign to recover their throne, and this may have been encouraged by Margaret of Austria. The king and queen had their state portraits painted on various occasions by artists working at the court of the governor of the Netherlands. In addition, a number of different versions of images of Christian II and Isabella of Austria have been conserved, and these may be linked to their visits to the different European courts they travelled to, as well as during the years that followed death of Margaret of Austria. For example, there are portraits linked to the workshops of artists active at the Mechelen court, such as Pieter van Coninxloo, Bernard van Orley, Jan Gossaert and Jan Cornelisz Vermeyen. The multiple versions of the king's portraits made by different artists hinder any attempt to date these panels with precision. On the basis of their formal characteristics, the version that could be related to the Christian's arrival in Mechelen following his exile is the one painted by an anonymous artist from the circle of Bernard van Orley, which is today conserved in the National Gallery of Denmark, Copenhagen (fig. 4). The portraits of Isabella of Austria include a variety of compositions, but, regrettably, the version attributed to Jan Gossaert, which formed part of the Tarnowski family collection, vanished during the Second World War.⁴² This painting could have been made by the artist in 1523, following Isabella's arrival in Mechelen from Denmark, or in 1524 following her return from the Imperial Diet (fig. 5). The strategy of constructing an image of the exiled monarchs' authority did not exclude their heirs, and Gossaert's portrayals of them echo the images of their parents in so far as the stylized mode of Habsburg child state portraiture permitted.

⁴¹ Rigsarkivet, København, München-Samlingen, B32, pk. 31, laeg nr. 10.

⁴² K. Grottowa, J. F. Tarnowski and W. Tarnowska, *Zbiory sztuki Jana Feliksa i Walerii Tarnowskich w Dzikowie, 1803-1849*, Wrocław, 1957, pp. 80-84.

Fig. 4. Circle of Bernard van Orley, *Portrait of Christian II of Denmark*, c. 1523-1526, Copenhagen, The National Gallery of Denmark, KMS3927.

Fig. 5. Jan Gossaert, *Portrait of Isabella of Austria*, 1523-1524, former collection Tarnowski, lost during the Second World War.

Raising a Danish prince and princesses

The princes of the kingdom of Denmark arrived with their parents in Mechelen in the spring of 1523 and remained there while their mother and father went in search of financial support. They remained at the court of Margaret of Austria, who was the member of the Habsburg family with the most experience in caring for minors. Following Isabella of Austria and Christian II's return to the Netherlands, they resided in Lierre and Zwijnaarde, close to Ghent. However, following Isabella's death, her husband sought to renew his efforts to win back his kingdom and once more left his descendants with Margaret of Austria.⁴³

John, their eldest child, was barely five years old when he arrived in the Netherlands. During Isabella's stays in Mechelen, the prince would spend time with his mother. Following her death, Margaret of Austria officially took on the role of mentor, and then following the latter's death in 1530, John remained in the custody of Mary of Hungary. John, along with the court of Charles V, attended the Imperial Diet of Regensburg in June 1532, where efforts were made to negotiate a compromise between the Catholic rulers

⁴³ A. Henne, *Histoire du règne de Charles-Quint en Belgique*, vol. 3-4, Paris, Madrid, Leipzig, 1858, p. 148.

and the Protestants. It was there that Christian II's eldest son, with the emperor's support, presented his father's claim to the Danish throne.⁴⁴ Unfortunately, the young prince died a few months later on 2 July 1532. Emperor Charles V, in a letter sent to his sister Mary of Hungary, underscored the grief he felt following the death of his favourite nephew: "...I have been touched by his death as I would that of a son of my own, for that is how I thought of him,"⁴⁵ that reveals an intimate and emotional relationship between them.

John had two sisters, as well as two twin brothers who died as infants between 1519 and 1520. Dorothea of Denmark left her parents' kingdom having just turned two, and like her brother, she remained in the care of Margaret of Austria. From an early age, and above all after her brother's death, Dorothea played an important role in the Habsburg marriage policy. She was eventually married to Frederick II, the Elector Palatine (1482-1556), with whom she sought to recover the Danish throne on various occasions, but without success.⁴⁶ Dorothea and her husband had no children, which had a major impact on the princess's political role. Furthermore, both sympathised with the Protestant reformation, which significantly reduced their possibilities as Habsburg allies. Following the death of Christian II, his daughter began to refer to herself as queen of Denmark, albeit without any political ramifications, as neither the empire nor its Scandinavian enemies recognised her claim. As an adult, Dorothea maintained close ties with her younger sister Christina, who she would visit or whose household she welcomed up until her death in 1580.

Christian II and Isabella's youngest daughter, Christina, was born on 10 November 1521, and she spent her childhood in Mechelen with her siblings. Before long, the princess was chosen to reinforce the empire's alliances through her marriage to the duke of Milan, Francisco II Sforza, in 1534. She was left a widow the following year and demanded her dowry back from the emperor, but in exchange, she was granted the rights to the city of Tortona.⁴⁷ Due to the conflict between the empire and the kingdom of France over their claims to the duchy of Milan, Christina returned to Flanders in 1537, and took up residence with Mary of Hungary in Ghent. Although negotiations were initiated for a second marriage to the English king, Henry VIII (1491-1547), the princess remained in the Netherlands until 1541, when she was married to Francis I (1517-1545), the son of Antoine, duke of Lorraine.⁴⁸ The couple had three children: Charles (1543-1608), Renata (1544-1602), and Dorothea (1545-1621). As a result of the Peace of Crépy, which was agreed between France and the empire in 1544, the duchy of Lorraine was declared independent, significantly increasing the couple's prestige. Unfortunately, just two years later, Christina became a widow for the second time, and she took over as regent in name

⁴⁴ K. Brandi, *Carlos V. Vida y fortuna de una personalidad de un imperio mundial*, Madrid, 1943; M. Lobo Cabrera, *Isabel de Austria. Una reina sin ventura*, p. 110-111.

⁴⁵ M. Fernández Álvarez, *Corpus documental de Carlos V, vol. 1*, Salamanca, 1997, p. 498.

⁴⁶ K. Brandi, *Carlos V. Vida y fortuna de una personalidad de un imperio mundial* (as in n. 41), p. 78-79.

⁴⁷ M. Lobo Cabrera, *Isabel de Austria. Una reina sin ventura*, p. 122.

⁴⁸ On the portrait of Christina of Denmark commissioned by Henry VIII and painted by Hans Holbein, see R. Strong, 'Holbein in England', *The Burlington Magazine*, 109, 770 (1967), pp. 276-281.

of her son Charles III of Lorraine, who was ten years old. She resided in Nancy until the French invasion in 1552, when she took refuge at the Imperial court. Due to the French monarchy's policy of regaining control over the duchy of Lorraine, Christina's eldest son married Claude of France (1547-1575), the daughter of King Henry II of France (1519-1559). However, the French monarch died in 1559, which permitted Christina to return to Nancy in 1560. Once Philip II of Habsburg approved her descendants' marriage policy (1527-1598), Christina's daughters were married to the rulers of the duchies of Bavaria and Brunswick-Lüneburg. The princess of Denmark negotiated with her sister for the rights to the royal throne. However, neither had the support from the Habsburg dynasty to recover their parents' rights to the throne. In 1578, Christina retired from political life and took up residence in Tortona, where she lived until she died in 1590.⁴⁹

The three princes were not granted the same status within the Habsburg family as their mother, nor did they feature in the correspondence between Margaret of Austria and Isabella of Austria. On the one hand, this can be explained by the more pressing issue of their parents' exile, which entailed a political struggle and significant financial demands, but also guaranteed their education in private and safety more as a family matter and not a state issue.

Nevertheless, an analysis of the education given to the previous generation of Habsburgs indicates how John, Dorothea, and Christina would have been taught in a similar conditions. Letters confirms that their safety, and privacy were conditions accomplished in the household. Furthermore, between 1526 and 1530, Margaret of Austria employed Éloy Clémentis, *maistre d'escole*, to take charge of the children's education.⁵⁰ It should be underscored that Erasmus of Rotterdam published his treatise on education, *De civilitate morum puerilium*,⁵¹ whereby it is very likely that the children of Christian II and Isabella were some of the first children to be taught with this work.

Another source for the education of princes is the series of portraits that can be understood as their state portrait, painted by Jan Gossaert when he served as court painter to Margaret of Austria.⁵² The different understanding of the sitter provided by the painter might also indicate a slight difference in the education of the princess in comparison with the prior generation. Gossaert was summoned to Mechelen in 1523 to restore some paintings from the collection of the Court of Savoy.⁵³ While there, he met with those children and made

⁴⁹ For further information on the life of Christina of Denmark, see J. Cartwright, *Christina of Denmark. Duchess of Milan and Lorraine. 1522–1590*, New York, 1913.

⁵⁰ A. Henne, *Historie du règne de Charles-Quint en Belgique*, vol. 6, Paris, Madrid, Leipzig, 1858, p. 43.

⁵¹ For a modern edition of this work see, Erasmus of Rotterdam, *A Handbook on Good Manners for Children: De Civilitate Morum Puerilium Libellus*, Toronto, 2008.

⁵² F. Winkler, *Die altniederländische Malerei: Die Malerei in Belgien und Holland von 1400-1600*, Berlin, 1924, p. 245; F. Baudson, *Van Orley et les Artistes de la Cour de Marguerite d'Autriche* (as in n. 5).

⁵³ J. Duverger, *Conrat Meijt (ca. 1480-1551)*, Brussels, 1934, p. 68; J. L. Burk, 'Conrat Meit: Court Sculptor to Margaret of Austria', in: D. Eichberger, ed, *Women of Distinction: Margaret of York/Margaret of Austria*, Leuven, 2005, p. 279; M. W. Ainsworth, 'The Painter Gossaert in His Artistic

several portraits of them (fig. 6). To date, at least eight copies of the same group portrait of three children have been identified, and these are attributed to Gossaert or his circle and as having been made in the 1520s.⁵⁴ This portrait of the children is not the only work by this artist related to the Danish royal family, as the aforementioned lost portrait of Isabella of Austria is also attributed to him (fig. 5).⁵⁵ Furthermore, Gossaert was in direct contact with Christian II while he resided at the court of Adolf of Burgundy (1489-1540) in 1526. There, the king commissioned him to design the funerary monument for his wife, which was to be installed in the church of St Peter in Ghent, and also a portrait of himself.⁵⁶ Therefore, his group state portrait of the children would have been painted between 1523, following the princes' arrival in the Netherlands, and 1526, when Christian II commissioned the funerary monument for the young sitters' mother.

Fig. 6. Jan Gossaert, *The Children of Christian II of Denmark and Isabella of Austria*, 1523 or 1526, London, The Royal Collection, RCIN405782.

Unlike the earlier state symbolical portraits of Habsburg children, Gossaert's composition stands out for its realist focus, which signals a key moment in the evolution of this pictorial genre. It is also noteworthy because the artist evidently found inspiration in the

Milieu', in: M. W. Ainsworth, S. Alsteens and N. M. Orenstein, eds, *Man, Myth and Sensual Pleasures. Jan Gossart's Renaissance*, New York, 2010, p. 16.

⁵⁴ M. W. Ainsworth, S. Alsteens and N. M. Orenstein, eds, *Man, Myth and Sensual Pleasures. Jan Gossart's Renaissance*, New York, 2010, p. 273.

⁵⁵ K. Grottowa, J. F. Tarnowski and W. Tarnowska, *Zbiory sztuki Jana Feliksa i Walerii Tarnowskich w Dzikowie, 1803-1849* (as in n. 42).

⁵⁶ M. Lobo Cabrera, *Isabel de Austria. Una reina sin ventura*, p. 91-92.

works of Albrecht Dürer (1471-1528).⁵⁷ The latter artist visited the court of Margaret of Austria on three occasions: firstly, in August 1520, when he met the governor of Brussels, and presented her with a set of his prints; Dürer's second visit to Mechelen was in June the following year when he visited the collection of artworks that had been sent to the Court of Savoy; and the Habsburg governor and the artist met again at a banquet organised by Christian II during a visit to the Netherlands on 7 July 1521.⁵⁸ Aside from frequenting the nobility, Dürer also met artists linked to the court and its cities. In his travel diaries, he expressed his personal appreciation for just two artworks, firstly, Jan van Eyck's altarpiece, the *Adoration of the Mystic Lamb* in Ghent, and secondly, Jan Gossaert's *Middelburg Altarpiece*, which was lost in a fire in 1568. It should also be noted that Gossaert admired the work of Dürer, which he copied on various occasions in his prints, such as his composition of *Adam and Eve*.⁵⁹ Aside from the fact that Gossaert knew the children's parents, he was one of the most widely renowned painters in the Low Countries.

In his portrait on panel, he depicted the three children, who may be identified, from the left, as Dorothea, John, and Christina; only John, in the centre, looks out at the spectator, while the girls express a sense of melancholy as they play with the apples and cherries on the table. The painting's uniform background is framed on three sides by a *tromp l'oeil* wooden frame, whereby the panel's composition is seemingly independent of the frame, which thus imitates a window. Due to the lack of more precise information, the space depicted in the painting cannot be established, but it could be the interior of some palace in Mechelen. However, its multiple repetitions indicate the sitters' prestige, as well as that of the author of this innovative composition that could be understood as the state portrait. Therefore, this portrait should be considered as part of the visual propaganda of the exiled Danish king, which was possibly intended to construct an engaging representation of his descendants.

Another composition that is also related to the Danish royal family, Jan Gossaert and child portraiture is the painting identified as a portrait of Dorothea of Denmark (fig. 7).⁶⁰ As is the case for the portrait of the three princes, the composition is framed by an illusionistic frame and has a uniform background. The sitter is distinguished by her garments, jewels and a device used for teaching astronomy. Dorothea holds an armillary

⁵⁷ L. Silver, 'Dürer and Gossaert', in: S. Foister and P. van den Brink, *Dürer's journeys: travels of a Renaissance artists*, London 2021, pp. 103-116.

⁵⁸ D. Eichberger, 'Art and entrepreneurship: Dürer's encounters with Margaret of Austria and his network at the imperial court', in: S. Foister and P. van den Brink, *Dürer's journeys: travels of a Renaissance artists*, London 2021, pp. 119-125.

⁵⁹ L. Silver, 'Dürer and Gossaert' (as in n. 57), pp. 103-111.

⁶⁰ L. Campbell, *The Early Flemish Pictures in the Collection of Her Majesty the Queen*, Cambridge, 1985, pp. 53-56. L. Campbell, *The Sixteenth Century Netherlandish Paintings, with French Paintings Before 1600* (as in n. 3), pp. 433-351.

sphere upside down and indicates a latitude with her finger.⁶¹ This gesture was interpreted by Lorne Campbell as a claim to her father's lost kingdom, as the girl approximately touches the latitude of the city of Copenhagen.⁶² It can be read as an attempt of the princes to be shown as a public persona, and legal heir to the kingdom. Undoubtedly, the inclusion of the armillary sphere, a didactic instrument, indicates that the princess received an erudite education that included elements of astronomy, that intentional was underline in the convention of the state portrait. Instruments such as armillary spheres would have formed part of the collection of the governor of the Netherlands. The portrait, like the previous composition, may be read as a further element of the visual strategy deployed by Christian II to underscore his family's noble origins, highlight their rights to the throne they had lost, and, above all, demonstrate the sitter's privileged education.

Fig. 7. Jan Gossaert, *A Young Princess (Dorothea of Denmark?)*, c. 1530-1532, London, The National Gallery, NG2211.

⁶¹ J. van der Stock, ed, *In search of Utopia: Art and science in the era of Thomas More*, Amsterdam, 2016, pp. 350-354.

⁶² L. Campbell, *The Early Flemish Pictures in the Collection of Her Majesty the Queen* (as in n. 3). Questions may be raised over this interpretation as the armillary sphere does not represent the planet earth with its latitudes, but rather the lines of latitude and longitude corresponding to the geocentric universe.

Conclusions

Margaret of Austria, as governor of the Netherlands and the figure responsible for the Habsburg's northern European policy, also assumed the role of educator of the young princes. The new trends promoted by her court, both in art and thought, were reflected in the education of the princes in her household. Therefore, Eleonor of Austria, Prince Charles, Isabella of Austria, and Mary of Hungary received an education that enabled and prepared them to undertake the task of government. In fact, for this generation of Habsburgs, it is possible to observe the city council's involvement with gifts, as well as assigned mentors and organization of public festivities. Sources on their upbringing are conserved that help to know the importance of children's education at the court. Furthermore, the Habsburgs did not overlook the visual dimensions of its political activity and the strategic use of art to reinforce the prestige of the princes brought up in Mechelen.

There are few sources for the education of the next generation and the period of Isabella of Austria's residence in Mechelen, and these only provide a limited insight into their childhood. However, those limits in describing children's lives show that exiled princesses might have enjoyed more privacy than their mother. The exchange of letters between Isabella and Margaret of Austria reveals that their health, well-being, and education were not overlooked, although they did not own the same prestige as their ancestors.

Privacy was regarded as a safety that should be guaranteed for proper domestic education. Due to the children's residence in Mechelen and their parents' status, the Danish princes were incorporated into Habsburg's policy of using art: their portraits were created at a young age by a prestigious artist. Furthermore, when Jan Gossaert created effigies of the Danish princes, he introduced a new, more realistic, and humanist trend into early sixteenth-century child portraiture to idealize them. The group portrait of the three princes, as well as the individual portrait, identified as Dorothea of Denmark, not only represent the protagonists, but these paintings depict the sitters' interest in learning and indicate how these heirs to a royal title were educated according to the latest pedagogical principles, and how courtly privacy for children changed in a decade. Still, sitters should understand those dynamics and the importance of their image, which was a part of their training to rule. Although their future status was uncertain due to the fate of their parents, the children were represented as adults ready to reclaim the Danish throne; despite this optimistic strategy, the outcome sought by the exiled King Christian II and his children would not come to pass.